

THE METHODOLOGY OF USING SONGS IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

To date, one of the most relevant areas of recent methodological research is the search for ways to teach effective speech communication. The relevance of raising this issue becomes obvious especially in our time, when the Russian language is the key to the success of business professional cooperation. This article substantiates the expediency of using songs at the initial stage of teaching Russian as a foreign language, describes the types of tasks, as well as the mechanisms of influence of music, songs on the motivation of listeners and cadets of higher military educational institutions.

Keywords: *methods of teaching the Russian as a foreign language, communicative method, the initial stage of teaching the Russian as a foreign language, artificial language environment, song in Russian lessons, language barrier, listening, higher military educational institutions.*

On October 14, 2022, at a meeting of the Council of CIS Heads of State in Astana, the leaders of the Commonwealth countries declared 2023 the year of the Russian language as an international communication in the CIS countries. The Russian language is an instrument for the development of cultural, social and economic ties in the CIS. Tatiana Shlychkova at the IIMC-2023 noted that "the Russian language is a tool that allows you to maintain an international dialogue. The CIS space is the most important platform for the development of such communication along with the countries of Africa, Latin America, etc." Russian as a foreign language in our case acts as a tool for the formation of professional competence of a serviceman. Consequently, successful mastery of it is an important condition for the formation of this competence, and as a result - the demand and competitiveness of graduates in the labor market.

At each meeting, in each of his addresses, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasizes the importance of learning foreign languages, as foreign languages help to learn the culture of another people, help to establish cooperation with the armies of

foreign countries. We believe that today every serviceman should be fluent in Russian, as we cooperate with such Russian-speaking countries of the world as the Russian Federation, Belarus, the Republic of Kazakhstan and others. Professional training of specialists of a military university that meets the requirements of state educational standards involves knowledge of special terminology, possession of skills and abilities to present educational material in various genres of scientific style, methods of processing and processing information, its use for educational and professional purposes.

The University of Public Safety trains cadets, students, as well as students of the correspondence department. The students of the correspondence department are employees of various structures of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. And the first question that all teachers of our university face is “How can you quickly and easily learn Russian?”, since in their official activities they often encounter people who do not speak Uzbek. For example, employees working at international airports, entering into a dialogue with citizens of the Russian Federation, must explain “what is where” or “where and how to get there”, in this regard, the topic of our research is quite relevant.

Also, from personal conversations with the students of the correspondence department, we learned that some of them find it difficult to speak Russian in the presence of Russian-speaking listeners and they prefer to remain silent in class for fear of making a mistake and causing classmates to laugh.

A well-known translator and psycholinguist D.N.Petrov claims that the cause of most problems with learning a foreign language are psychological blocks [Boychuk E.I., Nemova, N.I., 2018;245]. We believe that the first step is to remove these blocks. Since we have an adult audience and they are all from different structures of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, we suggest using songs in Russian language classes to relieve psychological blocks and tension among listeners. The songs help to create an artificial language environment, immersion in Russian reality, show real socio-cultural stories and comment on them, expand the scope of the language environment through verbal and non-verbal means, thus introducing listeners not only to the educational, but also to real discourse [Galskova N.D., Gez N.I., 2006; 47].

K.A. Lukyanova notes that in Russian language classes, you can use songs that are not highly artistic at all. Especially the use of such songs is relevant for levels A1 and A2, when students are not yet ready to analyze “deep” and “complex songs” [Lukyanova K.A., 2019;236]. T.B.Vasilyeva in her work devoted to the problem of selecting authentic song material at the initial stage of teaching Russian as a foreign language, notes that access to speech is possible only if students have an interest, and

therefore identifies as the most important linguistic methodological principle of song selection “the principle of influencing the emotional and motivational sphere of the individual, taking into account age characteristics and interests” [Vasilyeva T.B., 2015;369].

According to V.Levy, music is one of the most effective ways to influence the feelings and emotions of the trainees, representing the strongest psychological motivator that penetrates into the hidden depths of consciousness. He also describes the fundamental functions that combine music and foreign languages:

- 1) physiological (promotes memorization);
- 2) psychological (promoting relaxation, unloading);
- 3) emotional (causing feelings);
- 4) socio-psychological (enhancing the dynamics in the group);
- 5) cognitive (contributing to the thought process);
- 6) the function of unconscious learning (complex language structures are learned on an unconscious level);
- 7) communicative (facilitating communication).

The very limited use of songs both quantitatively and qualitatively at the initial stage of teaching the Russian language in higher military educational institutions, as well as a relatively small number of scientific and methodological works on this topic, in our opinion, indicate that the use of songs in the beginning adult audience remains underestimated [Medina S. L., 2002]. Meanwhile, at the initial stage, when students are just forming an attitude to a new language for them and, in fact, to study it, working with songs with a powerful emotional and energy charge seems no less important and necessary than at other stages [Rodionova N.N., 2012;115]. Thus, the **aim of research** is to substantiate and prove the effectiveness of the use of songs at the initial stage of teaching Russian as a foreign language in higher military educational institutions.

A song is an effective method of influencing the feelings and emotions of cadets and listeners, and one of the ways to distract them a little with the routine of educational activities [Baranova N.A., 2016; 46].

I.Yu.Pashkeeva in her article “The use of songs in teaching a foreign language” says that “the practical use of songs in Russian language classes is not a new technique. But for most teachers, the presence of music in the classroom seems to be something frivolous, distracting from studying. However, this is not the case. Music, songs in the classroom can become good assistants, provided that the material is carefully selected correctly” [Pashkeeva I.Yu., 2014;362].

I.P.Gubina also highlights the following methodological advantages of songs in teaching Russian as a foreign language:

– a song is a means of stronger assimilation and expansion of vocabulary, as it includes new words and expressions. In the songs, the already familiar vocabulary is found in a new contextual environment, which helps to activate it. Proper names, geographical names, realities of the country of the language being studied, poetic words are often found in songs. This contributes to the development of students' horizons, sense of language, knowledge of its stylistic features;

– grammatical constructions are better assimilated and activated in songs;

– songs contribute to the improvement of foreign language pronunciation skills, the development of musical hearing. It has been established that musical hearing, auditory attention and auditory control are closely related to the development of the articulatory apparatus. Learning and performing short, simple melodic songs with frequent repetitions help to consolidate the correct articulation and pronunciation of sounds, the rules of phrasal stress, rhythm features, etc.;

– the songs contribute to the aesthetic education of students, team building, and a fuller disclosure of everyone's creative abilities.

– songs and other musical compositions stimulate monologue and dialogical utterances, serve as the basis for the development of speech-thinking activity of cadets, contribute to the development of both prepared and unprepared speech.

– the song is a reflection of the existing picture of the world of native speakers, it reflects fears, anxieties, problems, joys, values, reflections, opinions, therefore, through the study of songs, someone else's culture is more deeply comprehended;

– with the help of songs, students come to understand and realize that each culture has its own specific features, features, that representatives of different cultures can see the same things in completely different ways, in other words, students form intercultural competence;

– for fruitful work with the song, the teacher must follow the rules for selecting songs: the content corresponds to the age of the students, melody, clear voice of the performer, rhythm, the presence of a linguistic and cultural component;

– songs create motivation for students to learn the Russian language, a positive attitude, and also develop students spiritually, form a musical ear, aesthetically develop them.

When choosing songs, it is worth adhering to certain criteria for complex work on the use of songs in Russian language classes:

1) Clarity. The song should not create additional difficulties for the perception of the material. Depending on the level of proficiency in Russian, you need to choose the tempo of the song.

2) The correspondence of the language material to the language level of foreign speakers. You should not choose songs with a lot of unfamiliar vocabulary and complex grammatical constructions [Gridneva N.A., 2017; 210].

3) Relevance. The song is selected taking into account the age of the cadets and taking into account the topic being studied. The current generation is different from the previous ones, they prefer light musical genres [Akhmedova, L.T., Lagai, E.A., 2016; 230].

4) Cultural conformity. The song should not contain too much slang, which can be confusing at the middle stage; taboo words, devalued vocabulary and should not carry a call to violence [Bystra E.B., Vlasenko O.N., Dorokhova E.Yu., 2019; 54].

5) The theme of the songs should not touch on "hot topics" (politics, national and religious affiliation, etc.) [Bolotova, Yu.V., 2017; 7].

Methodical methods of working with a song in higher military educational institutions

Below we propose a system for working with specific songs (text, tasks). A video sequence is also attached to the songs during the lesson.

Methodological development № 1

(based on the song “Идет солдат по городу”, Russian vocal and instrumental ensemble “Flame”)

Level: B1

Lexical and grammatical material: Accusative case, present tense of the verb

Task № 1. Check out the table.

проводить <i>кого? куда?</i>	Ещ spend
идти <i>куда? с кем?</i>	to go
обижаться <i>на кого?</i>	to be offended
ждать <i>кого?</i>	to wait
попить <i>что?</i>	to drink
купить <i>что? кому?</i>	to buy
торопиться <i>куда?</i>	in a hurry
выйти <i>откуда?</i>	get out
жить <i>где? с кем?</i>	to live

Task № 2. Listen to the song 3 times and insert the missing words.

У солдата _____ пуговицы в ряд

Ярче солнечного _____ золотом горят

Часовые на посту, в городе _____

Проводи нас до ворот, товарищ _____,

Товарищ _____

Идёт солдат по городу, по незнакомой _____

И от улыбок девичьих вся улица _____

Не обижайтесь девушки, но для _____ главное,

Чтобы его далёкая, любимая _____

А солдат попьёт кваску, купит _____

Никуда не торопясь, выйдет из _____

Карусель его помчит, музыкой звеня

И в запасе у него останется _____,

Останется _____

Идёт солдат по городу, по незнакомой _____

И от улыбок девичьих вся улица _____

Не обижайтесь девушки, но для _____ главное,

Чтобы его далёкая, любимая _____

Где любимая живёт, липы шелестят

И садится в карусель не её _____

Но другие ни к чему, все до одного

Если только верно ждёшь _____ своего,

_____ своего

Task № 3. Put the verbs in the past tense: ***проводить, купить, жить, ждать, идти.***

Task № 4. Write out all the nouns and translate them into Uzbek.

Task № 5. Determine the case of nouns: ***у солдата, до ворот, по улице, для солдата, из кино, на посту, по городу.***

Task № 6. Answer the questions:

1. Who has a day off?
2. Who accompanied the soldier to the gate?
3. What time of the year is described in the song?
4. What is important for a soldier?

Task № 7. Write down all pronouns and translate them into Uzbek.

Task № 8. Translate phrases into Uzbek and make sentences with them: ***купит эскимо, попьёт кваску, садится в карусель.***

Task № 9. Write out new words and make sentences with them.

Methodological development № 2
(based on the song “Я – это ты”, Murat Nasyrov)

Level: B1

Lexical and grammatical material: Declension of personal pronouns

Task № 1. Check out the table.

говорить <i>о чем? с кем?</i>	to speak
твердить <i>что? кому?</i>	to repeat
понять <i>что?</i>	to understand
видеться <i>с кем? когда? где?</i>	to see
уйти <i>куда? с кем?</i>	to leave
наступить	to come

Task № 2. Listen to the song 3 times and insert the missing words.

Пусть говорят, мы редко видимся с _____
 В сердце всегда ты со мной, ты со _____
 Пусть говорят, что не _____ нам быть вдвоём
 Люди твердят об одном, об одном, но
Я – это Ты
Ты – это Я
И _____ не надо нам
Всё, что сейчас есть у _____
Я лишь тебе одной отдам
 Лето _____ и наступили холода
 Но всё равно _____ нужна ты одна
 Вряд ли поймёт тот, кто не любит и не _____
 А за окном снег идёт, _____ идёт, но
 Пусть говорят, мы редко видимся с _____
 В сердце всегда ты со мной, ты со _____
 Пусть говорят, что не _____ нам быть вдвоём
 Люди твердят об одном, об одном, но
Я – это Ты
Ты – это Я
И _____ не надо нам
Всё, что сейчас есть у _____
Я лишь тебе одной отдам
 Лето _____ и наступили холода
 Но всё равно _____ нужна ты одна

Вряд ли поймёт тот, кто не любит и не _____

А за окном снег идёт, _____ идёт, но

Task № 3. Determine the tense of the verb: *отдам, твердят, видимся, говорят, прошло, наступили, поймет, ждет, любит.*

Task № 4. Write down all pronouns and translate them into Uzbek.

Task № 5. Determine the case of pronouns and make sentences with them: *со мной, с тобой, нам, у меня, тебе, мне, я, ты.*

Task № 6. Write down all the adverbs and translate them into Uzbek.

Task № 7. Write out new words and make sentences with them.

Task № 8. Sing this song.

Methodological development № 3

(based on the song «Кап-кап-кап (Маруся)», Boris Kuznetsov and Lev Polosin)

Level: A2

Lexical and grammatical material: The present tense of the verb. Adjective name

Task № 1. Check out the table.

прощаться	to say goodbye
молчать	to be silent
плакать	to cry
капать	to drip
петь	to sing
вернуться	to return
счастье	happiness
сосна	Pine tree
грусть	Sadness
душа	of the Soul
кап-кап	Drip-drip

Task № 2. Listen to the song 3 times and insert the missing words.

Зелёною _____ под старую _____

С _____ Ванюша прощается.

Кольчугой он звенит и нежно говорит

Не плачь, не плачь,

Маруся-красавица.

Маруся молчит и слёзы льёт,
 От _____ болит душа её.
 Кап-кап-кап из ясных глаз Маруси
 Капают слёзы на _____.
 Кап-кап-кап из ясных _____ Маруси
 Капают горькие, капают кап-кап,
 Капают прямо на копьё.
 Студёною _____ опять же под сосной
 С _____ Ванюша встречается.
 _____ вновь звенит и нежно говорит -
 Вернулся я к _____, Раскрасавица.
 Маруся от _____ слёзы льёт,
 Как гусли _____ её поёт.
 Кап-кап-кап из ясных _____ Маруси
 Капают слёзы на копьё.
 Кап-кап-кап из ясных _____ Маруси
 Капают сладкие, капают кап-кап,
 Капают прямо на _____.
 Маруся от счастья слёзы льёт,
 Как _____ душа её поёт.
 Кап-кап-кап из ясных глаз Маруси
 Капают слёзы на _____.
 Кап-кап-кап из ясных _____ Маруси
 Капают сладкие, капают кап-кап,
 Капают прямо на _____.

Commentary on the song

<i>Кольчуга</i>	- armor woven from iron rings, a metal net for protection from being hit by cold weapons.
<i>Гусли</i>	- Russian folk stringed plucked musical instrument, in general, representing a resonator body with 5-20 strings stretched over it, forming a diatonic scale. They belong to the family of zithers, psaltery with a game window — to the lyres.
<i>студёная зима</i>	Very cold.
<i>раскрасавица</i>	1. A very beautiful woman. 2. Someone or something distinguished by extraordinary beauty.

Task № 3. Write down all the verbs from the lyrics of the song, conjugate them and make sentences with them.

Task № 4. Write down all the pronouns and translate them into Uzbek.

Task № 5. Determine the case of pronouns and make sentences with them: *от счастья, на коньё, под сосной, из ясных глаз.*

Task №. 6. Write down all the adjectives and translate them into Uzbek.

Task № 7. Sing this song.

In order to determine the effectiveness of working with the song in the Russian language classes, a training experiment was conducted, which allowed to determine the quality of knowledge, skills and abilities of cadets and students of the correspondence department on the problem under study.

Thus, we came to the conclusion that the song can be used to form lexical, phonetic, spelling and grammatical skills at the initial stage of teaching Russian as a foreign language in higher military educational institutions.

The use of songs in the classroom unites cadets and listeners, increases interest in learning the Russian language. We also consider it appropriate to give cadets and listeners not only songs on military topics, but also modern mobile and light songs to keep up with the times.

The logical continuation of this research will be an increase in the number of songs with developed tasks.

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